

GENDER PERSPECTIVES IN LOCAL GOVERNANCE: INCLUSIVITY IN PUBLIC SPACES IN THE PROVINCE OF CAVITE

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explore the gender perspectives in local governance, particularly in the context of inclusivity in public spaces in the Province of Cavite. The paper employed a qualitative research approach which allowed an in-depth exploration of gender perspectives in local governance and inclusivity in public spaces in the Province of Cavite. Results showed that there was a serious underrepresentation of women in Cavite's municipal government. This underrepresentation of women in local government is a serious problem with far-reaching consequences. Gender discrimination is a physical reality that coworkers experience, rather than an abstract problem. The lack of diverse gender representation can lead to decisions that do not consider the needs and perspectives of marginalized genders, which can be detrimental to effective governance.

Keywords: *Gender and Development (GAD), Gender Perspective, Gender Equity, Women's Empowerment, Local Governance, Participatory Governance*

INTRODUCTION

There has been an increasing awareness germane to the role that gender plays in determining the experiences and interactions that people had in the public sphere. It is possible that local governance, which is the closest contact between residents and the government, has the ability to play a crucial role in the promotion of gender equality, inclusion, and social justice. When this potential is taken into consideration, it becomes very necessary to investigate the manner in which gender views are included into the decision-making processes, the creation of policies, and the general administration of public spaces at the provincial level.

For the purpose of investigating the complex link that exists between gender and the administration of the local government of the province of Cavite, with its long and illustrious history, diverse cultural traditions, large and massive influx of migration, and dynamic economic environment, provides an interesting case study. When it comes to tackling gender-related problems, this area serves as a microcosm of the larger difficulties and possibilities that local governments confront (Gu, et. al., 2024). This study was aimed to provide valuable insights that can be used to influence policy development, empower marginalized voices, and ultimately contribute to a more inclusive and equitable Cavite by scrutinizing the existing policies, practices, and attitudes towards gender inclusivity within the provincial government and its public spaces.

The reason for this research was because there is a dearth of thorough knowledge and recording of gender representation and inclusion in local government and public places within the unique context of the province of Cavite.

Studies have been undertaken on gender perspectives in local government and public places (Hervías et.al, 2023); however, the unique dynamics and issues that are present in the province of Cavite have not yet been thoroughly investigated.

As denoted in the Gender Equality Observatory for Latin America and the Caribbean (GEOLAC, 2024), the significance of this gap lies in the fact that it impedes the establishment of efficient policies and practices that suit to the specific socio-cultural setting of the local government.

In addition, there is a need for further empirical research about the experiences and perspectives of individuals of various genders in the province of Cavite with relation to their involvement and representation in local administration and public places. This kind of information is essential for determining the obstacles that stand in the way of gender inclusion and developing solutions to overcome those barriers (Lowe, 2024).

Through the provision of an in-depth examination of gender perspectives in local government and public places in the local government of Cavite, this study sought to address the gaps that have been identified. It is possible that the results may contribute to a more general discussion on gender inclusion and will provide information that will

influence policymaking and practice in the local government in particular and the national government in general.

Research Questions

Cavite, like many other areas, confronts obstacles in establishing gender equality in local administration and public places. The current level of gender representation in local government is inadequately documented, and it is unknown how existing rules and practices may encourage or obstruct gender inclusion. Furthermore, there is a dearth of thorough awareness of various genders' experiences and perspectives of their engagement and representation in local administration and public places.

This condition necessitates the creation and execution of effective gender inclusiveness measures. However, the details of such tactics, as well as how they might be adjusted to the Province of Cavite's distinct setting, have to be investigated. As a result, the purpose of this research is to look into these challenges in order to contribute to the development of gender inclusion in the Province of Cavite.

1. What is the current state of gender representation in the local governance of the Province of Cavite?
2. How do existing policies and practices promote or hinder gender inclusivity in public spaces in the Province of Cavite?
3. What are the experiences and perceptions of different genders regarding their participation and representation in local governance and public spaces?
4. What strategies can be implemented to improve gender inclusivity in local governance and public spaces in the Province of Cavite?

Theoretical Lens

In 2020, former CHED Commissioner, Dr. Jo Mark M. Libre introduced the theory of Gender and Development in Local Governance. This theory focuses on mainstreaming the implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) in local governance. It acknowledges the role of the government, especially its leadership, in the delivery of GAD services and the involvement of civil society.

The theory acknowledges the role of the government, especially its leadership, in the delivery of GAD services and the involvement of civil society. It addresses gender and development problems by mainstreaming GAD policy. The theory suggests that the level of knowledge and implementation of GAD provisions among local officials can significantly impact policy implementation.

The following literatures provides an in-depth investigation of a variety of aspects that involve Community development, public places, inclusivity, and local governance are all terms that come up.

Núñez (2020) investigates the process of integrating fragmented regions into inclusive public spaces via the introduction of municipal governance in Lima, Peru. The results of this study underline the crucial role that governance systems play in the formation of urban landscapes and the development of inclusive communities. Nunez emphasizes the need of developing localized decision-making mechanisms in order to respond to the distinct needs of various groups in his study of the situation in Lima. This results in the transition of formerly fragmented public areas into cohesive public spaces geared to accommodate a bigger population.

Akhila's research (2023) shifts the focus to India, especially Kerala, and explores the viewpoints and opinions of Dalit Elected Women Representatives in local government and politics. The study focuses on Kerala in particular. In addition to shedding light on the problems that Dalit women face in the political arena, the study provides critical insights on the dynamics of local governance among oppressed communities. Akhila's work not only emphasizes the need of inclusive representation, but it also emphasizes the importance of having effective policies and support structures in place to ensure the meaningful participation of underrepresented groups in local community government.

Fiorentino and Bartolucci (2019) study new governance concepts within the context of the sharing economy, therefore providing a technical point of view to the current discourse. Their research focuses on the use of blockchain technology for the intelligent administration of shared office spaces, presenting a fresh approach to urban planning and development. Local governments may employ blockchain technology to increase transparency and efficiency in the management of common areas. This will ultimately benefit the community while also enabling them to investigate creative solutions to the problems linked with urban governance.

Purcell underlines the importance of community development in the context of local strategic partnerships in his 2014 advocacies for public participation in newly developed spaces for local governance. The results of this study show the necessity of including communities in decision-making processes, as well as the ways in which collaboration among many stakeholders may result in more successful and inclusive governance systems. Purcell's work serves as a reminder of the critical role that grassroots participation plays in the process of developing new ways of local governance.

Malsch and O'Dwyer (2021) present an alternate point of view by exploring the topic of auditing research. Their major emphasis is on conceptual repair and technological disruptions that arise within local professional governance. This research highlights the need for flexibility in contemporary governance systems by acquiring a knowledge of the nature of governance practices that are always evolving. According to the study's conclusions, it is critical for local governments and experts to regularly update their working practices in order to stay up with the fast-paced technology and the ever-changing needs of society.

Certomà, Chelleri, and Notteboom (2020) develop the notion of 'fluid governance' in urban public areas. This concept provides insight into the informal planning techniques

employed in Rome. This research underlines the need of having adaptable governing structures in order to adequately manage ever-changing urban environments. This emphasizes the need of keeping governing approaches adaptable in order to respond to the ever-changing needs of urban populations. This will guarantee that public spaces remain vibrant and responsive to the communities they serve.

Fitch et al. (2023) widen the scope of the discourse by studying the intersection of feminism and public relations within the context of city governance. Their study offers light on the varied obstacles and opportunities that women in these diverse regions face by presenting perspectives from Australia, Indonesia, and Malaysia. The work provided here emphasizes the importance of gender-inclusive governance practices and the role that public places play in the achievement of gender equality.

Dalu and Manyani (2020) provide a gender-centered perspective in their discussion of gender inclusion and progress in South African public urban areas. Their study's results underline the critical role that inclusion plays in urban planning and governance, especially when it comes to gender equality. The study emphasizes the importance of policies and practices that provide safe and inviting public spaces for people from all walks of life. These locations should encourage not simply physical access, but also a sense of belonging and empowerment.

Makakavhule and Landman (2020) developed the concept of deliberative democracy by examining the democratic administration and design of public places in Tshwane, South Africa. They have shown through their work that public places may serve as hubs for democratic engagement and community involvement programs. Local governments may foster a more inclusive and participatory form of governance by creating public spaces that encourage dialogue and participation.

Using Cagayan de Oro City in the Philippines as an example, Yasay (2018) adds to the continuing debate by examining the role of civil society involvement as a vital component of efficient governance. This study underlines the importance of gender-specific issues being considered within the context of local government procedures, as well as the importance of civil society organizations actively participating in these processes. Yasay's work indicates how civil society participation may lead not just to more transparent decision-making but also to the promotion of gender-sensitive policies and increased accountability, ultimately contributing to the achievement of gender equality in government.

Cruz (2020) examines the governance environment at the national level in the Philippines, focusing on the role of the National College of Public Administration and Governance in the country's growth. Despite the fact that the study focuses primarily on the challenges of leadership and identity in public administration, it does make a brief reference to the crucial issue of gender and development. In order to establish successful national government, a gender-responsive approach must be used to effectively fulfill the unique needs and concerns of women. Cruz's research provides an opportunity to consider how gender-inclusive leadership and identity could exist in the realm of public

administration. This may be achieved by pushing for laws and practices that encourage women's empowerment and participation in decision-making processes.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A qualitative research design was used in this study. The qualitative method enables an in-depth examination of gender perspectives in local government and inclusion in public places in Cavite Province. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions were used to get insights into the experiences and attitudes of various genders.

Research Locale

The respondents were wide-ranging group of people living in selected districts of Cavite Province. Purposive sampling was used to guarantee that the results reflected diverse profile of genders, age groupings, and socio-economic backgrounds.

Research Instrument

An interview guide and a focus group discussion guide was among the research tools. During the interviews and focus group sessions, these instructions were utilized to assist in-depth exchanges.

Data Gathering Procedure

Face-to-face interviews and focus group discussions were used to gather data. The interviews and focus group discussions was be performed by qualified researchers and audio-recorded with the participants' agreement.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to find common themes and patterns in the responses from the qualitative data. Coding the data, recognizing themes, analyzing, and refining the themes, and eventually defining and naming the themes are all part of this process. The researchers will do the analysis manually, guided by the research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gender representation, inclusivity, and equity are critical aspects of any society's governance and public spaces. In the Province of Cavite, the examination of these dimensions has revealed a complex landscape influenced by various factors, policies, and practices. This discussion delves into the findings derived from a series of interviews centered around four key research questions:

1. What is the current state of gender representation in the local governance of the Province of Cavite?
2. How do existing policies and practices promote or hinder gender inclusivity in public spaces in the Province of Cavite?
3. What are the experiences and perceptions of different genders regarding their participation and representation in local governance and public spaces?
4. What strategies can be implemented to improve gender inclusivity in local governance and public spaces in the Province of Cavite?

Through thematic analysis, this discussion explores the insights gained from these interviews, addressing the current status of gender representation, the efficacy of existing policies and practices, the experiences and perceptions of different genders, and the strategies that can drive positive change. The findings unearth both challenges and opportunities on the path towards fostering a more inclusive and equitable society in Cavite.

Research Question 1 - Current State of Gender Representation

Underrepresentation of Women

Currently, women are significantly underrepresented in the local government of Cavite. Out of the 40 seats in the council, only four are occupied by women, making it just 10% representation.

-IDI 1

In the local government, the gender imbalance is quite noticeable. Women hold only a minority of positions, with men dominating the majority of seats.

-FGD 1

The answers from IDI 1 and FGD 1 both highlight the serious underrepresentation of women in Cavite's municipal government. These comments offer insight on the scope of the issue, in which women hold just a tiny percentage of seats, equating to barely 10% representation. This underrepresentation of women in local government is a serious problem with far-reaching consequences. For starters, it denotes a lack of diversity and inclusion in decision-making bodies. When women are underrepresented, it is more probable that policies and decisions will fail to fully incorporate women's views and needs, perhaps leading to governance biases.

Furthermore, such a gender disparity may deter women from pursuing careers in politics and municipal government. Women may be discouraged from pursuing professions in public service if they perceive restricted chances for progression and influence within these settings. The replies emphasize the need of taking proactive actions to solve this problem. To achieve a more balanced and fair representation in local government, strategies such as encouraging women's candidacy, imposing gender quotas, and building supportive settings for female leaders should be investigated.

Tokenism

It appears that women often hold symbolic roles in local governance. They are often appointed to positions that have limited decision-making power, which can be seen as tokenism.

-IDI 2

This statement illustrates a key problem within the Cavite Province's local government: the practice of allocating women to posts with minimal influence and responsibility. This is an obvious case of tokenism, in which women are put in posts just to create the impression of gender diversity, rather than being given meaningful opportunity to develop policy or participate in decision-making processes.

Tokenism may have a number of negative consequences. For starters, it may result in the marginalization of women's views and opinions by excluding them from important debates and decision-making processes. Second, it may promote gender stereotypes by saying that women are unsuitable for positions of leadership or decision-making. Finally, symbolic appointments may damage the legitimacy of gender equity measures while failing to address the core causes of gender inequality.

To counteract tokenism, local administrations in Cavite must guarantee that women in positions of leadership have genuine decision-making capacity and are not restricted to symbolic roles. This necessitates a commitment to gender-inclusive leadership that appreciates varied viewpoints and actively engages women in policy and governance choices.

In the researcher's observation, women in local government often occupy roles that seem more symbolic than substantial. Their positions lack real influence or authority

-FGD 2

FGD 2 validates the conclusion made by IDI 2 that women in local government in Cavite are typically restricted to symbolic positions. Interviewee 2 emphasizes, like Interviewee 1, that these jobs generally lack the power and influence required for meaningful involvement and decision-making.

The interviewees' agreement highlights the need for a more fair and inclusive approach to female representation in local government. Tokenism not only fails to solve gender imbalances, but it also diminishes women's potential contributions in leadership positions.

To address this issue, the Province of Cavite must establish policies and procedures that guarantee women in local government occupy positions of meaningful influence and responsibility. Gender representation should go beyond symbolism to enable women to contribute meaningfully to policy creation, governance, and decision-making. Cavite can promote a more inclusive and productive local government by using the different viewpoints and talents of both genders.

Research Question 2 - Policies and Practices Impacting Gender Inclusivity

Inadequate Gender Policies

There are some policies, but they are inadequately enforced and lack specificity in addressing gender-related issues. There is a need for more comprehensive and effective policies.

-IDI 3

Yes, there are policies, but their impact is limited due to poor enforcement and a lack of clear guidelines on promoting gender inclusivity.

-FGD 3

IDI 3 and FGD 3 are major concerns in the province of Cavite. While these rules exist, they are plagued by inadequate implementation, a lack of precision, and ambiguous guidance. These shortcomings limit the province's capacity to provide an inclusive and equal environment for all genders.

To solve this problem, a full review and reengineering of gender policy is urgently required. These rules should be improved, made more detailed, and accompanied by clear implementation guidance. Furthermore, enforcement procedures must be put in place to guarantee that these rules are not just words but are effectively implemented. Cavite can only advance toward a more inclusive and equitable governance and public space environment that respects and promotes the rights and dignity of all its people, regardless of gender, via strong, well-defined, and successfully implemented gender policies.

Stereotyping and Bias

Unfortunately, gender stereotypes and biases are still prevalent in our workplace. Women are sometimes viewed as less capable in decision-making roles, which hinders their progress.

-IDI 4

Yes, there are instances of gender bias where women's abilities are underestimated or overlooked in favor of male colleagues, perpetuating stereotypes

-FGD 4

Stereotyping and gender prejudice, as indicated by IDI 4 and FGD 4, are systemic concerns that must be addressed in order to achieve greater gender inclusion in local government and public places in Cavite. These prejudices not only impede women's advancement, but also restrict the potential contributions of people of other genders. To overcome this, efforts should be directed at increasing awareness of these prejudices, challenging assumptions, and fostering an environment in which all persons, regardless of gender, are valued for their talents, experiences, and credentials. Implementing diversity and inclusion programs, as well as encouraging equal opportunities, may assist in breaking down these obstacles and fostering a fairer society.

Research Question 3 - Experiences and Perceptions of Different Genders

Gender-Based Discrimination

I have colleagues who have experienced gender-based discrimination, which has had a negative impact on their confidence and willingness to participate actively.

-IDI 5

According to IDI 5, gender discrimination is a physical reality that coworkers experience, rather than an abstract problem. This shows that prejudice is a structural issue within Cavite's municipal government setting, rather than an isolated or anecdotal matter. The detrimental effect on trust and active involvement highlights the terrible ramifications of such discrimination. Individuals who are discriminated against may be less inclined to participate actively in governance, resulting in a loss of important views and contributions. This underscores the need of addressing and eliminating prejudice in order to create a more inclusive and fairer workplace for all genders.

Our colleagues oftentimes experience gender-based discrimination, which we believe contributes to a negative impact on their confidence and willingness to participate actively in politics and governance in the local government unit, not only in the city/municipal level, but at the provincial level as well.

FGD 5

FGD 5 confirms the existence of gender-based discrimination, adding that it has produced a hostile atmosphere for certain people. This underlines the negative impacts of prejudice, which may create an unwelcoming environment that discourages people from participating in local government and public areas. The phrase "hostile" emphasizes the gravity of the situation, implying that it goes beyond basic discomfort and may be very destructive. This conclusion emphasizes the need of addressing and eliminating gender-

based discrimination in order to create a more supportive and inclusive workplace in which all persons feel comfortable and encouraged to participate actively.

Lack of Representation

The lack of diverse gender representation can lead to decisions that do not consider the needs and perspectives of marginalized genders, which can be detrimental to effective governance.

-IDI 6

The remark made by IDI 6 mirrors the reality of many places, including Cavite. When specific genders are underrepresented in governance, decision-making may fail to consider their distinct views, needs, and concerns. As a result, policies that ignore crucial concerns impacting disenfranchised genders may be implemented, perpetuating disparities. Furthermore, persons from underrepresented groups may be discouraged from actively engaging in local administration, fearing that their concerns would not be heard. In the absence of diverse representation, government may become less responsive to the whole community it serves.

When there is a lack of diverse gender representation, it can result in policies and decisions that do not adequately address the concerns of all community members, leading to potential exclusion.

-FGD 6

This is an important consequence of a lack of gender diversity in governance. When decision-makers do not represent the community's diversity, they may unwittingly emphasize certain concerns while ignoring others. This exclusionary strategy has the potential to reinforce structural inequities while leaving underrepresented genders feeling ignored and unheard. To guarantee that policies and choices are inclusive and equitable, it is critical to address this problem by actively supporting and fostering varied gender representation in local government.

Research Question 4 - Strategies for Improvement in Gender Inclusivity

Gender-Sensitive Policies

One important step is to develop and enforce gender-sensitive policies that guarantee equal opportunities and representation for all genders.

-IDI 7

This response correctly emphasizes the need of gender-sensitive policies in encouraging diversity. The focus on "equal opportunities and representation" demonstrates a comprehension of the primary goals of such programs. However, it is critical to remember that just having rules in place is not enough; they must also be enforced and implemented. To achieve gender inclusion, clear and concrete policies that

address particular gender-related concerns must be developed and continuously implemented.

We should prioritize the creation of gender-sensitive policies and ensure they are consistently implemented to promote inclusivity.
-FGD 7

This comment strengthens the feeling expressed by the previous respondent, underlining the need of taking preemptive actions. Prioritizing the development of such policies is consistent with the notion that policy development is a critical step in resolving gender-related concerns. The focus on "consistent implementation" is critical since policies are only successful if they are implemented and tracked over time.

Training and Education

Stakeholders can be sensitized through comprehensive training and education programs that raise awareness about the importance of gender diversity and inclusion.
-IDI 8

The role of education and awareness in achieving gender inclusion is emphasized in IDI 8. Training programs may be an important tool for sensitizing stakeholders, such as government officials, workers, and the general public, to the importance of gender diversity and inclusion. These workshops may help people understand the underlying reasons of gender gaps and prejudices, resulting in a more inclusive atmosphere. Training and education efforts may help to dismantle preconceptions, prejudices, and discriminatory behaviors in the Cavite local government setting by providing chances for conversation and learning.

Educational programs and workshops can help stakeholders understand and address gender-related issues, fostering a more inclusive environment.
-FGD 8

This comment emphasizes the importance of educational programs and seminars in fostering an inclusive atmosphere. Such programs might go beyond increasing awareness to provide stakeholders with practical knowledge and skills to successfully handle gender-related challenges. These programs allow people to actively contribute to the development of gender inclusion by promoting conversations and giving tools for detecting and overcoming prejudices. Furthermore, educational initiatives help overcome knowledge gaps between genders, resulting in more courteous and inclusive interactions in local government and public areas

Conclusions

Various major conclusions resulted from an examination of the existing status of gender representation, policies and practices, experiences, and possible initiatives for

increasing gender inclusion in local government and public spaces in the Province of Cavite.

According to the report, women are significantly underrepresented in municipal government, with women occupying just a minority of roles. Because of this underrepresentation, choices may be made that ignore the concerns of disadvantaged genders and perpetuate gender inequities. Existing gender rules are often ineffective and lack definition, resulting to a climate in which gender preconceptions and prejudices prevail.

Gender-based discrimination and concerns of uneven representation are common, deterring underrepresented groups from actively participating. However, potential reform initiatives have been found, such as the formulation and implementation of gender-sensitive laws, comprehensive training, and education programs, the encouraging of varied candidacies, and the remodeling of public areas to be more inclusive.

Recommendations

Based on the theme analysis and results, the following suggestions are made to improve gender inclusion in the Province of Cavite's local government and public spaces:

1. The government , particularly the province of Cavite should evaluate and enhance current gender policies to ensure they are comprehensive, actionable, and successfully implemented. There should be clear standards and systems in place for reporting and resolving gender-related concerns.

2. Make frequent and required training programs and seminars available to government officials, workers, and stakeholders. These initiatives should emphasize gender diversity, inclusivity, and the abolition of preconceptions and prejudices. Regular reviews should be carried out to measure their effectiveness.

3. Encourage people of different genders to run for local office. Give them assistance, mentoring, and resources to help them campaign successfully. Implement policies to lower the obstacles to entrance for underrepresented women in politics.

4. Work with urban planners and architects to adapt public areas to be more inclusive. Ensure that public areas are secure, accessible, and friendly to people of all genders, considering their unique needs and experiences.

5. Begin public awareness efforts to educate the public about the value of gender inclusion in government and public places. Encourage people to take an active role in promoting gender equality and reporting prejudice.

6. Create gender diversity and inclusion committees or task groups within local government authorities. These committees may track progress, gather data, and make policy recommendations to improve gender equality.

7. Invest in data collecting and research to better understand the province's distinct difficulties and requirements for various genders. This information may help to develop evidence-based policies and practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations based on the principles of Bryman and Bell (Cited from the study conducted by Mizra, et.al. (2023) were considered such as:

Respondents of the research were not harmed nor coerced; Respect for the dignity of respondents/participants were considered by respecting and always treating them nicely during this study; Full consent for research was obtained from the respondents/participants. At the start of the data collection, the necessary procedures/processes for research were established for respondents to avoid conflicts, issues and other concerns; Privacy of the respondents/participants was ensured. All information collected will be kept confidential. Anonymity was also ensured. The identities of the respondents will be kept confidential and will never be disclosed to anyone except with the consent of the respondents in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The Data Privacy Act, also known as Republic Act No. 10173, is a law that seeks to protect all types of information, whether private, personal, or sensitive. It is intended to apply to both natural and legal persons involved in the processing of personal information.

Maintaining the stand that the gathered information was and will only be used for the purpose of this study; Deceptions and exaggerations were avoided; The researcher disclosed her profile, including the graduate school where she comes from, and the rationale for collecting the data; All types of research communication were conducted with honesty and transparency. All communications, such as requests for data collection procedures, were made available. Any type of misleading information or representation of primary data in a biased manner was avoided and no misleading information were provided.

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